

Title: Energy and morphology of martensite – twinned martensite interface in CuAlNi shape memory alloy : A phase-field study

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Description: The dataset associated with this publication contains the finite-element codes and the simulation results related to the phase-field study of the needle-like twins within the transition layer at the martensite–twinned martensite interface.

Methodology: The finite-element codes were developed by using the AceGen system and the simulations are performed in AceFEM, both add-on packages of Mathematica. The postprocessing of the results has been done in the open-source platform Paraview.

File Formats: Finite-element codes are in .c format. The results are in two formats, the plot data in .csv format and the visualization data are in .vtk format.

Size: 15 GB

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Access Instructions: The full dataset is available upon request due to storage limitations. Contact Mohsen Rezaee Hajidehi (mrezaee@ippt.pan.pl)

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